

Methodology of Evaluating the Activation Energy of Oxygen Reduction Reaction on Pt/C Electrode in High Temperature H₃PO₄

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Keywords: High-temperature PEM fuel cells, rotating rod disc electrode, Pt catalyst, activation energy, oxygen reduction reaction, phosphoric acid

Abstract

High temperature proton-exchange membrane fuel cell (HT-PEMFC) technology is widely studied alternative to current energy conversion technologies based on fossil fuels. Compared to solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs), HT-PEMFCs allow more flexibility and demand less operation control due to their lower temperature. On the other hand, HT-PEMFCs show an advantage over low-temperature PEMFCs in terms of less demand on the purity of the H₂ used, the possibility to recover the generated heat, lower water management requirements, and easy heat management. One of the critical limitations of HT-PEMFC operation is a slow kinetics of the cathodic reduction of O₂ (ORR) due to presence of H₃PO₄ which ensures proton conductivity in the system. Electrochemical dynamic methods such as cyclic voltammetry or linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) can be used to determine the kinetic parameters of ORR. These measurements can provide information on the Tafel slope and exchange current density (j_{ex}) of the ORR. However, performing these measurements under conditions relevant for HT-PEMFC operation is challenging due to presence highly concentrated H₃PO₄ and elevated temperature. First, determination of the kinetic parameters requires correct assessment of equilibrium potential of ORR (E_{ORR}). The value of the E_{ORR} is generally influenced by the activity (fugacity) of the reactants and products and the temperature, a discussion of the appropriate standard states of the components is also necessary. Second, the relationship between the j_{ex} and the reaction rate constant (k°), necessary for calculation of activation energy (E^\ddagger), must be known. It includes consideration of the likely reaction mechanism. In this paper, the methodology for appropriate determination of E^\ddagger was developed and used for estimation of E^\ddagger of ORR from LSV curves measured on commercially available Pt/C catalyst under HT-PEMFC relevant conditions. In particular, the measurements were carried out using a rotating glassy carbon rod disk electrode (RRE) in purified 98 wt.% H₃PO₄ (as electrolyte) at

temperatures of 120, 140, 160, 180 °C. Though the treatment was developed in context of ORR and HT-PEMFC, the approach is generally applicable to any electrochemical reaction.

Graphical Abstract

List of Abbreviations

FC	Fuel cell
GC	Glassy carbon
HT	High temperature
LSV	Linear sweep voltammetry
MSE	Mercury-mercurous sulphate electrode
ORR	Oxygen reduction reaction
PBI	Polybenzimidazole
PEMFC	Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
RDS	Rate-determining step
RHE	Reversible hydrogen electrode
RRE	Rotating rod disk electrode

List of Symbols

A	pre-exponential factor in Arrhenius equation	various units
$a_{H^+,aq}$	activity of solvated H^+ in H_3PO_4	1
$a_{H_2O,g}$	activity of gaseous H_2O above H_3PO_4	1
$a_{H_2O,l}$	activity of liquid H_2O in H_3PO_4	1
$a_{O_2,l}$	activity of dissolved O_2 in H_3PO_4	1
$a_{O_2,g}$	activity of gaseous O_2 above H_3PO_4	1
a_{OOH^*}	activity of adsorbed OOH^*	1
a_{OH^*}	activity of adsorbed OH^*	1

a_{\odot}	activity of free adsorption site	1
$c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	molar concentration of H_2O in H_3PO_4	mol m^{-3}
c_{H^+}	molar concentration of H^+ in H_3PO_4	mol m^{-3}
c_{O_2}	molar concentration of O_2 in H_3PO_4	mol m^{-3}
c_{Ox}^{S}	molar concentration of oxidised species close to eld. surface	mol m^{-3}
$c_{\text{Red}}^{\text{S}}$	molar concentration of reduced species close to eld. surface	mol m^{-3}
c_{OOH^*}	surface molar concentration of OOH^*	mol m^{-2}
c_{OH^*}	surface molar concentration of OH^*	mol m^{-2}
c_{st}^*	standard surface molar concentration (1)	mol m^{-2}
c_{\odot}	surface molar concentration of free adsorption site	mol m^{-2}
c_{st}	standard molar concentration (1000)	mol m^{-3}
D_{O_2}	diffusion coefficient of O_2 in H_3PO_4	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
E^{\ddagger}	activation energy	J mol^{-1}
E	electrode potential	V vs. RHE
$E^{\circ'}$	formal potential	V vs. RHE
E_T°	standard redox potential at given T	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR},T}$	equilibrium potential of ORR at given T	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR},T}^{\circ}$	standard redox potential of ORR at given T	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR},l,T}^{\circ}$	standard redox potential of ORR, liquid H_2O as product	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR},g,T}^{\circ}$	standard redox potential of ORR, gaseous H_2O as product	V vs. RHE
$E_{\text{ORR},T}^{\circ'}$	formal potential of ORR	V vs. RHE
f	correction factor for geometry of RRE versus RDE (1.25)	1
F	Faraday's constant (96 485)	C mol^{-1}
ΔG_r°	standard molar Gibbs energy of reaction	J mol^{-1}
$\Delta G^{\circ\ddagger}$	standard Gibbs energy of activation	J mol^{-1}
j	geometric current density	A m^{-2}
j_{lim}	limiting current density	A m^{-2}
j_k	kinetic current density	A m^{-2}
j_{RDS}	current density of rate determining step	A m^{-2}
j_{ex}	exchange current density	A m^{-2}
j_{red}	partial reduction current density	A m^{-2}
j_{ox}	partial oxidation current density	A m^{-2}
k	reaction rate constant	various units
k_{eff}	effective reaction rate constant	various units
k_{RDS}	reaction rate constant of rate determining step	various units
k°	standard reaction rate constant	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
k_{dis}°	st. reaction rate constant of ORR in dissociative mechanism	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
k_{as}°	st. reaction rate constant of ORR in associative mechanism	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
\overleftarrow{k}	reaction rate constant in oxidation direction	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
\overrightarrow{k}	reaction rate constant in reduction direction	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
\tilde{k}°	parameter proportional to k°	$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$

K_x	equilibrium constant of O ₂ adsorption	1
n	number of exchanged electrons	1
ΔS_r°	standard molar entropy of reaction	J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
$p_{st.}$	standard pressure (101 325)	Pa
$p_{H_2O,T}^*$	vapour pressure of pure liquid H ₂ O at T	Pa
$p_{H_2O,T}$	vapour pressure of H ₂ O above H ₃ PO ₄ at T	Pa
$p_{O_2,T}$	partial pressure of O ₂ above H ₃ PO ₄ at T	Pa
R	universal gas constant (8.314)	J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
R^2	coefficient of determination	1
T	thermodynamic temperature	K
t	temperature	°C
x_{H_2O}	molar ratio of H ₂ O in H ₃ PO ₄	1
α	charge transfer coefficient	1
β	symmetry factor	1
γ_{H_2O}	activity coefficient of H ₂ O in H ₃ PO ₄	1
γ_{O_2}	activity coefficient of O ₂ in H ₃ PO ₄	1
γ_{H^+}	activity coefficient of H ⁺ in H ₃ PO ₄	1
γ_{OOH^*}	activity coefficient of adsorbed OOH [*]	1
γ_{OH^*}	activity coefficient of adsorbed OH [*]	1
γ_{\odot}	activity coefficient of free adsorption site	1
η	overpotential	V
ν	kinematic viscosity	m ² s ⁻¹
φ_{O_2}	fugacity coefficient of O ₂	1
φ_{H_2O}	fugacity coefficient of H ₂ O	1
ω	revolution rate	rad s ⁻¹

1 Introduction

High temperature fuel cells with proton exchange membrane (HT-PEMFC) are a type of fuel cell with very promising application potential. Their advantages over low-temperature PEM fuel cells are their heat recovery capabilities, they do not require complex water-management and tolerate hydrogen of significantly lower purity (e.g. they are not sensitive to CO poisoning in concentration of up to 3 vol.%) [1-3]. Since HT-PEMFCs are operated at temperatures of 160-200 °C [4], polybenzimidazole (PBI) doped with high concentration of H₃PO₄ is widely used as PEM [5, 6].

For an energy efficient operation of a fuel cell, it is essential to maximise the rates of kinetics of electrode reactions, i.e. to minimise the polarisation overvoltage. It is usually the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR), taking place in the cathode catalyst layer, which is responsible for the most significant losses. ORR has slower kinetics compared to the hydrogen oxidation

reaction taking place at the anode side and limits the whole process [7-9]. The ORR catalyst in HT-PEMFC is typically based on Pt metals or their alloys [10-13]. One of the parameters that determines the rate of the electrode reaction is the exchange current density, j_{ex} , i.e. the absolute value of partial current density at the equilibrium potential of ORR, E_{ORR} (a higher j_{ex} value corresponds to a faster kinetics of the ORR at E_{ORR}). However, in the context of HT-PEMFC, it is often problematic to determine the E_{ORR} of an ORR half-reaction because it depends on the temperature and activities of products and reactants [14-16]. The literature is inconsistent in its approach and often does not consider an influence of reactant/product activities in H_3PO_4 [13, 17-22] on resulting E_{ORR} (while considering change of the standard redox potential value E_{ORR}° with temperature) and sometimes even use ($E_{ORR}^\circ = 1.229$ V), i.e. E_{ORR}° value valid at 25 °C of the ORR [10, 23-26] as an equilibrium potential E_{ORR} at higher temperatures. This necessarily leads to incorrect j_{ex} values. Moreover, as will be shown below, even knowledge of j_{ex} values at various temperatures is not sufficient for correct calculation of activation energy (E^\ddagger).

The dependence between reaction rate constant k and E^\ddagger or in this case Gibbs energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) is given by the Arrhenius equation, **Eq. 1**

$$k = A e^{\frac{-\Delta G^\ddagger}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where A represents pre-exponential factor, R universal gas constant and T thermodynamical temperature. In the case of elementary electrochemical reaction ($Ox + ne^- \rightleftharpoons Red$), the current density j can be calculated from the values of the rate constants of backward (oxidation) and forward (reduction) reaction \vec{k} and \overleftarrow{k} , respectively, according to **Eq. 2**:

$$j = nF(\overleftarrow{k}c_{Red}^S e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F\eta}{RT}} - \vec{k}c_{Ox}^S e^{\frac{-\beta F\eta}{RT}}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where n represents number of exchanged electrons (in case of elementary reaction generally $n = 1$), F is Faraday constant, $c_{Red/Ox}^S$ represent concentrations (close to electrode surface) of the reduced and oxidised specie involved in the redox reaction, β is symmetry factor and η represents overpotential. However, situation in the case of ORR is significantly more complex since ORR is far from being an elementary reaction. Moreover, it involves several adsorbed intermediates. Therefore, finding dependence between system composition and j or j_{ex} and in turn between j_{ex} and k becomes more complicated.

This paper aims to suggest more appropriate methodology for calculation of E_{ORR}° and E_{ORR} at temperatures around these relevant for HT-PEMFC operation, i.e. in the range from 120 to 180 °C. This involves consideration that the actual H_2O activity/concentration (as a product of ORR), H^+ and O_2 activity/concentrations (as a reactants of ORR) vary with T under these

conditions. The different approaches to calculating the E_{ORR} , the choice of standard states and availability of the data (equilibria, activity coefficients, concentrations, etc.) in the literature will be discussed as well.

The second objective of this paper is also to outline, appropriate estimation of ΔG^\ddagger of ORR from determined j_{ex} values of ORR on a Pt catalyst in H_3PO_4 in the discussed temperature range.

2 Experimental

2.1. Used chemicals and materials

The commercially available catalyst HiSPEC4000 (40 wt.% Pt on carbon black) (Johnson-Matthey, UK) was used as the investigated Pt/C catalyst. The following chemicals were also used in the work: 85 wt.% H_3PO_4 (extra pure, Acros Organics), 30 wt.% H_2O_2 (per analysis, non-stabilised, Lach-Ner), N,N-dimethylformamide (per analysis, Penta), 10 wt.% solution of polybenzimidazole in N,N-dimethylformamide (PBI Performance products), O_2 (99.5%, SIAD) and N_2 (99.99%, SIAD). Demineralised water (conductivity $< 0.5 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) used during the work was prepared by DIWA 3rica system (WATEK, Czechia).

H_2O_2 was used for purification of commercial H_3PO_4 [27, 28] from H_3PO_3 which is electrochemically active in the ORR potential region [29]. The 85 wt.% H_3PO_4 was mixed with the 30 wt.% H_2O_2 in volumetric ratio of 2:1. The mixture was poured in a PTFE beaker, heated to 160 °C and left at this temperature for 24 h. Prepared H_3PO_4 was poured in a glass storage bottle while still hot. The concentration of thus purified H_3PO_4 was then determined by acid-base titration. Titration was performed using automatic titrator, (Easy Pro, Mettler Toledo), with 0.1 M NaOH (Standard solution, Penta) serving as a titration agent. The concentration of H_3PO_4 was $97.6 \pm 0.6 \text{ wt.}\%$ (i.e., $70.9 \pm 0.4 \text{ wt.}\%$ P_4O_{10}), which also corresponds to the observed density ($1.849 \pm 0.006 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$), in accordance with the literature [30, 31]. Thus prepared H_3PO_4 was used for all measurements.

2.2. Set-up for rotating rod disk electrode (RRE) measurement

The measurements were carried out in a PTFE vessel (100 cm^3) placed in a heating mantle (WiseTherm WHM, Witeg) heated to desired temperature and containing purified 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 as an electrolyte. All measurements were performed with EC301 potentiostat (Stanford Research Systems, UK). A rotator with rotation control (AFMSRXE, Pine Research, USA) was used in combination with an in-house made shaft. The shaft was constructed from a CNC axis with centering and adjusted to a precise diameter on a lathe [32, 33]. The temperature was controlled automatically by an in-house made temperature controller and monitored by a

thermocouple (5SRTC, Omega, USA) placed in a glass tube. The counter electrode was a roll of Pt foil with an area of about 7 cm² separated from the main compartment of the electrolyte by a ceramic frit. A Hg|Hg₂SO₄ in saturated K₂SO₄ solution (MSE), 0.654 V vs. RHE (Monokrystaly, Czechia) was used as a reference electrode. It was separated from the H₃PO₄ environment by a double junction, the first one filled with 97.6 wt.% H₃PO₄, the second with saturated K₂SO₄ solution. The second junction was placed in a short Liebig cooler tempered to 25 °C by a cryostat (Julabo F12). The cell was sealed with PTFE tape (DuPont).

The working electrode itself was a glassy carbon rod (Sigradur[®] G, HTW, Germany) of 5 mm diameter and 6 cm length. Before each ink deposition, the electrode disk was polished with a sandpaper (MicroCut P4000, Buehler, USA) and then with a suspension of alumina (0.3 μm) on felt. To prevent the ink loss from the RRE disk during catalyst application, its sides were wrapped with several layers of PTFE tape. The thin film electrodes were prepared according to the following procedure: 2.5 mg of catalyst was dispersed in 10 cm³ of acetone to achieve an overall Pt concentration of 0.1 g dm⁻³. The mixture was homogenised in an ice bath using an ultrasonic probe (Sonoplus MS73, Bandelin, Germany) for 30 minutes, power 12 W. To achieve final Pt loading of 10 μg cm⁻², a total of 20 mm³ of ink was applied dropwise (2 mm³ per drop) to the GC rod base using a micropipette (Eppendorf). After each drop, the surface of the disk was allowed to dry at room temperature. In order to prevent an agglomeration of catalyst in ink suspension during thin film preparation, the ink was vigorously stirred with a PTFE magnetic bar (1 cm length) at 500 rpm using stirrer (MR3004, Heidolph, Germany). Then, for immobilisation of the thin film on the surface of the electrode, 4 mm³ of PBI solution in dimethylformamide (concentration of 0.5 g dm⁻³) was applied in two drops on the surface of the thin film. The PBI solution was vigorously stirred at 500 rpm for at least 1 h before and during deposition. The prepared RREs were dried at ambient temperature and stored in a dry box under N₂. The PTFE tape was removed after final drying.

Each prepared electrode was first cycled 3 times in the potential range of 0.3 V to -0.05 vs. MSE (sweep rate 100 mV s⁻¹) in the N₂ saturated electrolyte (saturation time 30 min) at RRE electrode without the rotation. Then, after saturation of the electrolyte with O₂ (saturation time 30 min), the LSVs were measured in the potential range of 0.3 V to -0.1 V vs. MSE at a sweep rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ on RRE at various revolution rates (400, 900, 1600 and 2500 rpm). Finally, the electrolyte was re-saturated with N₂ (saturation time 30 min) and LSVs were repeated at the same settings. These measurements were then used as a background that was subtracted from the previous LSVs measured in the O₂-saturated electrolyte. All measurements were performed at various temperatures (from 120, 140, 160 to 180 °C) using the same electrode. The potentials

measured using MSE reference electrode (at each temperature) were recalculated to RHE scale using values reported previously [34, 35], see **Eq. 3**.

$$E_{\text{RHE},T} = 0.54 \text{ V} - (t - 160 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}) \cdot 0.00015 \text{ V }^\circ\text{C}^{-1} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where 0.54 V is $E_{\text{MSE},433\text{K}}$ and t is temperature in $^\circ\text{C}$.

All voltammograms were corrected for the IR drop during the measurements. The Savitzky-Golay filter (cubic, frame length 7 points) was used to smooth the measured data. To ensure reproducible results, each measurement was performed in triplicate and with at least three different working electrodes.

3 Results

3.1 Equilibrium potential of ORR

As discussed in the introduction, for determination of j_{ex} values at given temperature (and consequently the ΔG^\ddagger), it is necessary to correctly determine corresponding $E_{\text{ORR},T}$, which requires knowledge of standard redox potential of ORR ($E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ$) and the activities (fugacities) of the involved components at given temperature [18, 19]. In HT-PEMFC, which operates at temperature between 160-200 $^\circ\text{C}$, it is not obvious at first sight whether H_2O is formed in the liquid phase or in the gaseous phase. This can be described by two different equations, **Eq. 4a** considers the formation of H_2O in the gaseous state at given T , **Eq. 4b** considers the formation of H_2O in the liquid state,

with corresponding cathode reactions being described by **Eq. 5a** and **Eq. 5b**.

$E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ$ of the reactions **Eq. 5a** and **Eq. 5b** can be calculated from the corresponding standard reaction Gibbs energies at given T , $\Delta G_{r,l}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{r,g}^\circ$ according to **Eq. 6** [36].

$$E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ = \frac{-\Delta G_{r,T}^\circ}{nF} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

For a reaction considering the formation of liquid and gaseous H_2O at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ (298 K), $E_{\text{ORR},l,298}^\circ = 1.229 \text{ V}$ vs RHE and the $E_{\text{ORR},g,298}^\circ = 1.184 \text{ V}$, respectively, using thermodynamic data [21]. $E_{\text{ORR},T}^\circ$ (at constant pressure of $p_{\text{st}} = 101\,325 \text{ Pa}$) can be calculated using **Eq. 7** [16, 36, 37],

$$E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}^{\circ} = E_{\text{ORR},298}^{\circ} + \frac{-\Delta S_{r,l/g}^{\circ}}{nF} \cdot (T - 298) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where ΔS_r° represents standard molar entropy of reaction, its value is $-326.7 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)}$ as a product of ORR and $-88.9 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$ as a product; corresponding slopes of $dE_{\text{ORR},T}^{\circ} / dT$ are $-0.8465 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$ and $-0.2302 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$, respectively.

Using the thermodynamic data, the resulting values of $E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}^{\circ}$ yielding liquid and gaseous H_2O are summarised in **SI 1**. **Figure 1** summarises in detail the E_{ORR}° and E_{ORR} from **SI 1** and **Table 2**.

Figure 1: Standard redox and equilibrium potentials for ORR in 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 at temperatures of 120-180 °C, for liquid or gaseous H_2O as a product. Equilibrium potentials were calculated using activities of components provided in Table 1.

To sum up, if the $E_{\text{ORR},l,T}^{\circ}$ and $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}^{\circ}$ values are compared, it is clear that at 100 °C the potentials are identical since chemical potentials of the liquid and gaseous H_2O at boiling point are equal.

Another step is calculating the equilibrium potentials, $E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}$, at various temperatures. It requires applying the Nernst equation and taking into account activities of the reacting components and products, see **Eq. 8**.

$$E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T} = E_{\text{ORR},l/g,T}^{\circ} - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l/g}^2}{a_{\text{O}_2,g} a_{\text{H}^+,aq}^4} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

The activity (fugacity) of reacting O_2 ($a_{\text{O}_2,g}$) can be calculated from partial pressure of O_2 , $p_{\text{O}_2,T}$, and standard pressure, p_{st} , using **Eq.9**,

$$a_{\text{O}_2,T} = \varphi_{\text{O}_2} \frac{p_{\text{O}_2,T}}{p_{\text{st}}} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where the fugacity coefficient $\varphi_{O_2} \approx 1$ can be considered in the context of the high temperatures and ambient pressure p used (in this case $p \approx p_{st.}$, measurements were carried out under normal atmospheric pressure). As the vapours above H_3PO_4 solutions up to a temperature of about 320 °C contain practically only H_2O [30, 38, 39] (at higher temperatures phosphorous(IV) oxide is found in the gas phase as well), pure O_2 brought to the system under these conditions will get saturated only with H_2O vapour. Therefore, $p_{O_2,T}$ can be expressed using **Eq. 11**,

$$p_{O_2,T} = p - p_{H_2O,T} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$p_{O_2,T}$ values for temperatures of 120-180 °C and H_3PO_4 concentrations of 97.6 wt.% (i.e., 70.9 wt.% P_4O_{10}) are summarised in **Table 1**, H_2O vapours pressure data from [38, 39].

Table 1: Relevant values of reaction species in 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 at different temperatures for $E_{ORR,T}$ calculation

$t / ^\circ C$	p_{H_2O} / kPa	$p_{H_2O}^* / \text{kPa}$	$a_{O_2,g}$	$a_{H_2O,g}$	$a_{H_2O,l}$	$a_{H^+,aq}$
120	5.687	198.670	0.944	0.056	0.029	0.010
140	12.473	361.540	0.877	0.123	0.034	0.010
160	25.441	618.230	0.749	0.251	0.041	0.010
180	48.728	1002.80	0.519	0.481	0.049	0.010

More difficult is a determination of proton activity $a_{H^+,aq}$, since the only value mentioned in the literature is the one for 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 at temperature 150 °C ($a_{H^+,aq} = 0.0102$) [40]. Therefore, in the absence of other data, this value was used for all temperatures within an interval of 120-180 °C despite the fact that is not possible to easily assess the error introduced into the calculation using this constant value.

For the reaction of **Eq. 5a** and **Eq. 5b**, it will be necessary to consider the different expressions for the H_2O activities, i.e. $a_{H_2O,l}$ and $a_{H_2O,g}$ for substituting into **Eq. 8**. In the case of H_2O vapour, its activity, $a_{H_2O,g}$, can be calculated as the ratio of $p_{H_2O,T}$ to $p_{st.}$, see **Eq. 12**,

$$a_{H_2O,g} = \varphi_{H_2O} \frac{p_{H_2O,T}}{p_{st.}} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

where φ_{H_2O} represents fugacity coefficient of H_2O . In the context of the elevated temperatures and ambient pressure, it can be assumed that $\varphi_{H_2O} \approx 1$. If the reaction is considered to produce liquid H_2O , $a_{H_2O,l}$ is equal to the ratio of $p_{H_2O,T}$ to the vapour pressure of pure H_2O at a given temperature ($p_{H_2O,T}^*$) (given in **Table 1**) according to **Eq. 13**. For further information see **SI 2**.

$$a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l} = \frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O},T}}{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O},T}^*} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

Focusing back on **Eq. 8**, it is now possible to calculate the $E_{\text{ORR},T}$ for ORRs yielding both liquid and gaseous H_2O (**Eq. 5a** and **Eq. 5b**). The resulting value of $E_{\text{ORR},T}$ will be the same for a given temperature for both the reactions written in the notation **Eq. 5a** (with $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)}$ as a product) and the reaction written in **Eq. 5b** (with $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$ as a product). The calculated values are summarised in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Equilibrium potentials for ORR in 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 at temperatures of 120-180°C, for liquid or gaseous H_2O as a product, consideration of changes in the activities of the species involved.

$t / ^\circ\text{C}$	$E_{\text{ORR},g,T} / \text{V}$	$E_{\text{ORR},l,T} / \text{V}$
120	1.056	1.053
140	1.031	1.027
160	1.005	1.000
180	0.978	0.971

As already mentioned, in HT-PEMFC it may not be obvious at if H_2O is formed in the liquid or in the gaseous phase. Due to equilibrium between the two, it is obvious that it should not matter which of the two options is chosen as long as appropriate thermodynamic treatment and data for activities of involved components are used. Indeed, the calculated $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$ and $E_{\text{ORR},l,T}$ potentials vary by less than one percent (in order of mV) over a wide range of temperatures. This is given by minor error in the literature thermodynamic data. Nevertheless, in the following chapters, the value of $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$ will be used preferentially because liquid-vapour equilibria for H_3PO_4 are much more covered by thermodynamic data in the literature than data required for calculation of the $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}$ in H_3PO_4 .

3.2 Evaluation of polarisation curves

The measured voltammetry curves are presented in **Figure 2**. It can be seen that the limiting current density j_{lim} and current densities in general raise with increasing temperature.

Figure 2: ORR polarisation curves at temperatures of 120-180 °C obtained at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt.% H₃PO₄, 5 mV s⁻¹, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, E_{ORR} values presented in SI 1, Hispec4000, 10 μg_{Pt} cm⁻²

According to Koutecky-Levich equation (**Eq. 14**), the measured current density contains contributions of the kinetic current density j_k and limiting current density j_{lim} ,

$$\frac{1}{j} = \frac{1}{j_{lim}} + \frac{1}{j_k} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

At high overpotentials, the reciprocal value of j_k can be neglected and the relation simplifies to $j \approx j_{lim}$, which can be expressed using formula known as Levich equation (**Eq. 15**),

$$j_{lim} = 0.62fnFc_{O_2}D_{O_2}^{2/3}\omega^{1/2}\nu^{-1/6} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

where $n = 4$ (considering four-electron reduction of O₂), $f (=1.25)$ is factor accounting for the different geometry of the RRE compared to the RDE [33, 41], ω represents revolution rate of rotating electrode, D_{O_2} is diffusion coefficient of O₂ in H₃PO₄, c_{O_2} is concentration of O₂ dissolved in H₃PO₄, and ν is kinematic viscosity of H₃PO₄ (values for different temperatures can be found elsewhere [8, 15, 30, 31, 40, 42-50]). Using the Levich equation, the product $c_{O_2}D_{O_2}^{2/3}$ can be estimated from experimentally determined j_{lim} values. The results are summarised in **Table 3**. As can be seen, the measured data show a very good agreement with the literature. It is good to point that the literature data for temperature range 160-180 °C were obtained by extrapolation from values at lower temperatures [15, 48] and experimental results presented in this work support their validity.

Table 3: $c_{O_2}D_{O_2}^{2/3}$ values calculated using Levich equation, determined from LSVs obtained at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, Hispec4000 $10 \mu\text{gPt cm}^{-2}$

t (°C)	$c_{O_2}D_{O_2}^{2/3}$, this work ($10^{-7} \text{ mol s}^{-2/3} \text{ m}^{-5/3}$)	D_{O_2} , ref. ($10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)	c_{O_2} ref. (mol m^{-3})	$c_{O_2}D_{O_2}^{2/3}$ ref. ($10^{-7} \text{ mol s}^{-2/3} \text{ m}^{-5/3}$)
120	2.07	2.14 @ 125	0.097 @ 125 °C [15]	1.61 @ 125 °C [15]
		[15]	0.41 [45]	2.41[45]
		0.45 [45]	0.31-0.35 [48]	1.82-2.06 [48]
140	3.36	No data	No data	No data
160	3.27	2.99 @ 150 °C	0.11 @ 150 °C [15]	
		[15]	0.40 @ 150 °C [45]	2.22 @ 150 °C [15]
		0.85 @ 150 °C	0.32-0.37 @ 150	3.59 @ 150 °C [45]
		[45]	°C [48]	
180	3.46	5.10 [15]		2.87-3.32 @ 150 °C
		extrapol.	0.11-0.18 [15]	[48]
		0.09 [47]	extrapol.	3.26-5.33 [15]
		extrapol.	0.36 [47] extrapol.	extrapol.
				3.38 [47] extrapol.

With the knowledge of j and j_{lim} , the values of j_k can then be calculated from **Eq. 14**. After plotting the decadic logarithms of the j_k values over the investigated potential range, Tafel plots are obtained, see **Figure 3**. The results of Tafel slope fitting, i.e. Tafel slopes (with corresponding charge transfer coefficients α) and exchange current densities j_{ex} are summarised in **Table 4**.

Figure 3: Tafel plots of ORR polarisation curves for temperatures of 120-180 °C, LSVs measured at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt.% H₃PO₄, 5 mV s⁻¹, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, E_{ORR} values are presented in SI 1, Hispec4000, 10 μg_{Pt} cm⁻²

Table 4: Summary of ORR kinetic parameters determined from Tafel plots at temperatures of 120-180 °C, LSVs measured at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 97.6 wt.% H₃PO₄, 5 mV s⁻¹, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding E_{ORR,g,T}, Hispec4000, 10 μg_{Pt} cm⁻²

$t / ^\circ\text{C}$	Tafel slope / mV dec ⁻¹	α	$j_{\text{ex}} / \text{mA m}^{-2}$
120	133 (R ² = 0.997)	0.584 ± 0.002	3.23 ± 0.01
140	127 (R ² = 0.989)	0.645 ± 0.007	6.27 ± 0.07
160	120 (R ² = 0.994)	0.716 ± 0.004	10.01 ± 0.06
180	108 (R ² = 0.994)	0.831 ± 0.005	14.21 ± 0.09

It can be seen that the Tafel slope decreases with decreasing temperature (this is consistent with [51-55]) and reaches a value of 120 mV dec⁻¹ @ 160 °C in 97.6 wt.% H₃PO₄, which is in agreement with the literature, see sources in SI 3. It can also be seen that the j_{ex} values increase with temperature. However, as will be discussed later, these values should not yet be used to determine ΔG^\ddagger . In any case, because $\alpha \approx 0.5$, it can be for the beginning assumed that the first electron transfer reaction represents a rate-determining step (RDS) in the whole ORR process. We are aware, that this assumption of $\alpha \approx 0.5$ is little questionable for $\alpha \approx 0.83$, determined for temperature of 180 °C. However, this α value is still lower than 1, which would correspond to different RDS.

3.2 Reaction rate constant - mechanisms of the reaction

In order to correctly determine the value of ΔG^\ddagger from Arrhenius type equation, it is necessary to find, how an effective reaction rate constant value of the whole the reaction sequence, k_{eff} , changes with temperature. To do that, the relation between j_{ex} and other parameters including concentration of the reactants/products and reaction mechanism, i.e. $j_{\text{ex}} = f(k^{\circ}_{\text{eff}}, c_{\text{H}^+}, c_{\text{O}_2}, c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, \text{mechanism})$ has to be determined. Considering that the reaction mechanism consists of series of elementary steps, the particular form of the dependence is influenced by both, the order and rates of individual elementary reactions. An analytical expression for $j_{\text{ex}} = f(k_{\text{RDS}}, c_{\text{H}^+}, c_{\text{O}_2}, c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})$ dependence can be easily derived if a so-called rate-determining step RDS with k_{RDS} exists (and its stoichiometry is known) in the reaction sequence. In the particular case of ORR, the overall reaction is a 4 e⁻ reduction process leading to H₂O (**Eq. 5a** or **Eq. 5b**). For the mathematical description of the rate of the whole reaction sequence, it is important to consider:

- pseudo-equilibrium of the reactions preceding the RDS
- rate of the RDS
- pseudo-equilibrium of the reaction following the RDS

Most authors assume that the mechanism of the ORR process begins with a chemical adsorption of O₂ on the surface of Pt. Depending on whether O₂ dissociates upon adsorption or not, two different ORR mechanisms can be distinguished, an associative or a dissociative one. The **dissociative path** is treated in **SI 5**. When the **associative path** of the ORR is considered to take place, the overall reaction is:

The adsorption of O₂ leads to O₂^{*} adsorbed on the Pt surface (**Eq. 17**).

Subsequently, this adsorbed O₂^{*} undergoes one-electron reduction to adsorbed OOH^{*} (**Eq. 18**).

The index "as" was introduced to indicate that it relates to the associative O₂ adsorption pathway. The literature suggests that this step represents the RDS [8, 16, 56]. This is also in agreement with our data showing that $\alpha \approx 0.5$. Therefore, it can be considered that experimentally determined α value corresponds to the value of the symmetry factor, β , of the first electron transfer reaction, i.e. **Eq. 18**. Further one-electron reductions and/or chemical steps follow. However, all the reactions proceeding after RDS can be assumed to proceed near equilibrium conditions, so it does not really matter what is exact mechanism of the remaining

part of ORR process and it is sufficient to consider only the overall remaining reaction, see **Eq. 19**.

The overall current density is proportional to the current density of the RDS (**Eq. 18**), j_{RDS} , as expressed by the kinetic equation (**Eq. 20**)

$$j = 4j_{\text{RDS}} = 4F\overleftarrow{k}_{\text{as}}c_{\text{OOH}^*}e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E-E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} - 4F\overrightarrow{k}_{\text{as}}c_{\text{O}_2^*}c_{\text{H}^+}e^{\frac{-\beta F(E-E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. 20}$$

where $E_2^{\circ'}$ is formal potential of the RDS, i.e. **Eq. 18** and c_{x^*} represent surface concentrations of individual adsorbed species. Assuming chemical equilibrium in step preceding the RDS (**Eq. 17**) a in **Eq. 21**,

$$K_1 = \frac{a_{\text{O}_2^*}}{a_{\text{O}_2}a_{\text{⊙}}} = \frac{\gamma_{\text{O}_2^*}c_{\text{O}_2^*}c_{\text{st.}}c_{\text{⊙}}^*}{\gamma_{\text{O}_2}c_{\text{O}_2}\gamma_{\text{⊙}}c_{\text{⊙}}c_{\text{⊙}}^*} \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

and when considering activity coefficients $\gamma_x = 1$, $c_{\text{O}_2^*}$ can be expressed using **Eq. 22**,

$$K_1' = \frac{c_{\text{O}_2^*}c_{\text{st.}}}{c_{\text{O}_2}c_{\text{⊙}}} \\ c_{\text{O}_2^*} = \frac{K_1'c_{\text{O}_2}c_{\text{⊙}}}{c_{\text{st.}}} \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

where K_1' is apparent equilibrium constant (dimensionless), $c_{\text{⊙}}$ represents molar surface concentration of free adsorption sites, the standard molar concentration ($c_{\text{st.}} = 1000 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$) and the standard surface concentration ($c_{\text{st.}}^* = 1 \text{ mol m}^{-2}$). Analogously, the derivation of the c_{OOH^*} is based on assuming pseudo-equilibrium in the overall remaining reaction after the RDS, i.e. **Eq. 19**, by means of Nernst equation (**Eq. 23**).

$$E_3 = E_3^{\circ} - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 a_{\text{⊙}}}{a_{\text{H}^+}^3 a_{\text{OOH}^*}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 23}$$

Rearrangement provides the desired result, see **Eq. 24**. The standard state used for the adsorbed species is based on recommendations provided in [57]).

$$E_3 = E_3^{\circ} - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 \cdot \frac{c_{\text{⊙}}}{c_{\text{st.}}^*}}{\frac{c_{\text{H}^+}^3}{c_{\text{st.}}^3} \cdot \frac{c_{\text{OOH}^*}}{c_{\text{st.}}^*}} \right) - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 \gamma_{\text{⊙}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^3 \gamma_{\text{OOH}^*}} \right) \\ E_3 = E_3^{\circ'} - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 \cdot \frac{c_{\text{⊙}}}{c_{\text{st.}}^*}}{\frac{c_{\text{H}^+}^3}{c_{\text{st.}}^3} \cdot \frac{c_{\text{OOH}^*}}{c_{\text{st.}}^*}} \right) \\ c_{\text{OOH}^*} = \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st.}}^3 c_{\text{⊙}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^3} e^{\frac{3F(E_3 - E_3^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. 24}$$

After substituting the relations **Eq. 21** and **Eq. 24** into **Eq. 20**, the overall kinetic equation **Eq. 25** of the overall reaction (**Eq. 16**) is obtained.

$$j = 4F\bar{k}_{as} \frac{x_{H_2O,l}^2 c_{st}^3 c_{\ominus}}{c_{H^+}^3} e^{\frac{3F(E_3 - E_3^{\circ'})}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} - 4F\vec{k}_{as} \frac{K'_1 c_{O_2} c_{\ominus} c_{H^+}}{c_{st}} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. 25}$$

Since the reference potential in **Eq. 20** is the formal potential $E_2^{\circ'}$ of the step in **Eq. 18**, it applies that $\bar{k}_{as} = \vec{k}_{as} = k_{as}^{\circ}$. If it is moreover considered that step in **Eq. 18** represents the RDS, it becomes obvious that this k_{as}° value should be used in determining ΔG^{\ddagger} of the whole ORR process, i.e. the purpose of following derivations is to find dependence $k_{as}^{\circ} = f(j_{ex}, c_{H^+}, c_{O_2}, x_{H_2O})$.

Having analytical expression for current density of the overall ORR process (**Eq. 25**) allows to investigate also the corresponding exchange current density, j_{ex} . This can be done by setting the electrode potential E equal to E_{ORR} as defined by Nernst equation for overall ORR process (**Eq. 8**). This corresponds to state with $j = 0$ and consequently $j_{ex} = -j_{red} = j_{ox}$, where j_{ox} and j_{red} correspond to the first and second term on the right side of the **Eq. 25** (and are usually called partial oxidation and partial reduction current density), respectively. Further operations with j_{red} are presented below, see **Eq. 26-27**. Corresponding treatment of j_{ox} is summarised in **SI 3**, see **Eq. A19-A20**.

$$-j_{ex} = j_{red} = -4Fk_{as}^{\circ} K'_1 c_{O_2} c_{\ominus} c_{st}^{-2} c_{H^+} e^{\frac{-\beta F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{H_2O,l}^2 c_{st}^5 c_{\ominus}}{c_{O_2} c_{H^+}^4 c_{st}^*} + (E_{ORR}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'}) \right)}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. 26}$$

After rearrangement, the **Eq. 27** is obtained.

$$-j_{ex} = j_{red} = -4Fk_{as}^{\circ} c_{H^+}^{1-\beta} c_{O_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{H_2O,l}^2 c_{\ominus} c_{st}^{-2+\frac{5\beta}{4}} \left\{ K'_1 e^{\frac{-\beta F(E_{ORR}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. 27}$$

Analogously to the above treatment of j_{red} , the development of the partial oxidation current density j_{ox} , i.e. the first term on the right side of **Eq. 25**, yields the very same dependence of j_{ex} on composition of the system. For details, see **SI 4**.

Considering that c_{\ominus} (in **Eq. 27** and **Eq. A20**) must be the same for both partial current density notations, j_{ox} and j_{red} differ (except for the sign) only by notation of constant terms. In particular, comparison of **Eq. 27** and **Eq. A20** yields **Eq. 28**, where the differences between $E_1^{\circ'}$ ($E_2^{\circ'}$) and $E_{ORR}^{\circ'}$ and K'_1 stand out.

$$e^{\frac{3F(E_{ORR}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'}) + F(E_{ORR}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} = K'_1 \quad \text{Eq. 28}$$

After taking logarithm of **Eq. 28** and substituting for formal potentials $E_x^{\circ'}$ and apparent rate constant K'_1 , equality **Eq. 29** can be obtained,

$$-4FE_{ORR}^{\circ'} = -FE_2^{\circ'} - 3FE_3^{\circ'} - RT \ln K'_1$$

$$-4FE_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^4 \gamma_{\text{O}_2}} = -FE_2^{\circ} - 3FE_3^{\circ} - RT \ln K_1 - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{O}_2}^*}{\gamma_{\text{O}_2} \gamma_{\odot}} - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 \gamma_{\odot}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^4 \gamma_{\text{O}_2}^*}$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ} = \Delta G_2^{\circ} + \Delta G_3^{\circ} + \Delta G_1^{\circ} \quad \text{Eq. 29}$$

which is consistent with Hess's law of the thermodynamic cycle supporting validity of the whole treatment. By excluding the mostly unknown but at given temperature constant terms (curly brackets) in **Eq. 27** or **Eq. A20**, the desired relation between k_{as}° and experimentally determined j_{ex} value at each particular temperatures is obtained, see **Eq. 30**. The only parameter, which is not easily available, is c_{\odot} . It is important to mention that, using **Eq. 30**, only relative changes of the k_{as}° denoted as $\tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^{\circ}$ could be obtained.

$$k_{\text{as}}^{\circ} \propto \tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^{\circ} = \frac{j_{\text{ex}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{2}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\odot}} \quad \text{Eq. 30}$$

However, if j_{ex} values are determined at various temperatures, variation of all parameters in **Eq. 27** (or **Eq. A20**) must be considered (recall that the c_{H^+} was assumed to be constant due to lack of data). It is obvious that values such as c_{\odot} , K_1' and difference $E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'}$ (or $E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'}$) are not easy to obtain and one is left with simplifying assumption that their values do not vary significantly with temperature. For example, it can be assumed that because of nature of (adsorption) process, K_1' value should decrease with increasing temperature, while value of c_{\odot} should increase, so it is possible that product $c_{\odot} K_1'$ will not change dramatically with temperature. Due to lack of data, it was assumed that the molar ratio of H_2O in H_3PO_4 $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ can be approximated by $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}$ (assuming is $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is proportional to $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}$) as defined by **Eq. 13**. If it is considered that the ORR process proceeds via **dissociative path** according to **Eq. A3**, **A4** and **A5**, the analogous treatment (see **SI 3**) yields **Eq. 31**.

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{red}} = -4Fk_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{2}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\odot} c_{\text{st}}^{-\frac{3}{2} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} \left\{ \sqrt{K_2'} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. 31}$$

Then, the result is the relation **Eq. 32**.

$$k_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} \propto \tilde{k}_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} = \frac{j_{\text{ex}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{2}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\odot}} \quad \text{Eq. 32}$$

It is currently unclear from the literature which ORR reaction pathway is preferred under the given conditions. Some authors mention the dissociative pathway as the preferred mechanism [58-61], but arguments can also be found for a RDS in the associative reaction followed by dissociation of the already absorbed molecular O_2 [62, 63]. Last but not least, the preference of the associative pathway depends on the Pt surface coverage and the ratio of c_{\odot} to c_{O_2} [37], the type of crystal lattices [64, 65] and temperature [65, 66].

3.3 Activation energy of ORR

The relationships developed in previous section were used to evaluate ΔG^\ddagger of ORR from the Arrhenius plots, i.e. $\ln \tilde{k}^\circ$ (with \tilde{k}° being proportional to k°) on $1/T$. **Figure 4** summarises the Arrhenius plots obtained using either directly experimentally determined j_{ex} or the above developed procedure leading to $\tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^\circ$ and $\tilde{k}_{\text{dis}}^\circ$. In particular, j_{ex} values were determined at equilibrium potentials $E_{\text{ORR},T}$ i.e. these corresponding to given temperature and system composition (120-180 °C, 98 wt.% H_3PO_4). Following treatment is valid assuming that

1. ORR proceeds via above assumed associative (or dissociative) mechanism,
2. the terms K'_1 , c_{\ominus} , c_{H^+} , $E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'}$ and $E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'}$ do not vary significantly with temperature,
3. it is possible to consider the condition that RDS is the electrochemical single-electron reduction (α is around 0.5), when $\alpha \approx 0.83$ (i.e. significantly greater than 0.5) at 180 °C.

Obtained j_{ex} values were then used to extract corresponding \tilde{k}° values, taking into account system composition (120-180 °C, 98 wt.% H_3PO_4) and β at each individual temperature for two different ORR mechanisms.

Figure 4: Calculated ΔG^\ddagger with consideration of corrections for $E_{\text{ORR},g,T}$ and reaction mechanisms, determined from LSVs obtained at RRE using revolution rates 2500 rpm; GC electrode, 120-180 °C, 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 , 5 mV s^{-1} , corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, Hispec4000, $10 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$

As can be seen in **Fig. 4**, both, the measured (left y axis) and corrected data (using **Eq. 30** or **Eq. 32**) (right y axis) show reasonable Arrhenius dependence. The error of the linear interpolation $\ln \tilde{k}^\circ$ vs. reciprocal T is not significantly different than using the apparent measured j_{ex} . A look at the results might suggest that the main reason for changes in slope of Arrhenius plot could be the change in $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, which increases by about 70% in the temperature interval of

120-180 °C. In contrast, the c_{O_2} only increases by about 20% over the investigated temperature interval. But if the effect of β in **Eq. 30** or **Eq. 32**, is considered, then the term $c_{\text{O}_2}^{1/2-\beta/4}$ increases by 70% in case of dissociative mechanism (in associative case $c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\beta/4}$ increases by 85%) in the temperature range of interest, while the term $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\beta/2}$ decreases only by 20%. The question is whether the use of **Eq. 30** or **Eq. 32**, which was derived by considering that the reaction mechanism contains only one RDS, which is the first electronation reaction, is correct if the α is already significantly greater than 0.5 at 180 °C (already 0.83). In any case, the resulting ΔG^\ddagger (+26.7 kJ mol⁻¹) value using $\tilde{k}_{\text{as}}^\circ$ is about a 25% lower than using j_{ex} (+36.6 kJ mol⁻¹), in the case of $\tilde{k}_{\text{dis}}^\circ$ (+29.0 kJ mol⁻¹) are values of ΔG^\ddagger about a 20% lower. However, it is the j_{ex} value that is normally used in the ΔG^\ddagger calculation, so ΔG^\ddagger values found in the literature for similar conditions are [15] +66.1 kJ mol⁻¹ in 98 wt.% H₃PO₄, [67] +54.8 kJ mol⁻¹ in 85 wt.% H₃PO₄, [68] +41.8 kJ mol⁻¹ in 85 wt.% H₃PO₄ or [20] +33.1 kJ mol⁻¹ in 85 wt.% H₃PO₄. The latter values are in an agreement with our results without considering the effect of the mechanism.

Thus, under HT-PEMFC operating conditions, the difference between the value of $\Delta G_{\text{as}}^\ddagger$ and G_{dis}^\ddagger found in the temperature range of 120-180 °C (difference is about 8%) seems to be negligible. However, if the ORR mechanism is known or, for example, two catalysts with similar composition are compared, the calculation can be based directly on the $\tilde{k}_{\text{dis(as)}}^\circ \propto j_{\text{ex}}$ relation for the corresponding ORR mechanisms. Conversely, ΔG^\ddagger value determined directly from j_{ex} values is overestimated which may lead to incorrect conclusions, cause inconsistencies with other methods of obtaining ΔG^\ddagger , etc.

4 Conclusion

The primary focus of this work was on the rigorous determination of ORR activation energy E^\ddagger from experimentally obtained ORR polarisation curves. Most importantly, it is strictly necessary to consider changes in equilibrium potentials with temperature, E_T . It was also shown, that the often used procedure based on determining E^\ddagger directly from exchange current densities $j_{\text{ex},T}$ (using correctly determined E_T values), is fundamentally incorrect. First of all, even in the case of elementary electrochemical reaction a nonlinear dependence (influenced by system composition and symmetry factor β) exists between, $j_{\text{ex},T}$ and standard rate constant, k_T° . Moreover, in the case of complex reactions, the particular form of the k_T° on $j_{\text{ex},T}$ dependence is influenced also by the reaction mechanism. If this reaction mechanism is known

and the rate determining step (with rate constant $k_{RDS,T}$) is present in the sequence of the elementary steps, an analytical solution in form $k_{RDS,T} = f(j_{ex,T})$ can be obtained. It is also good to point out that the formula, in case of complex reactions, contains (generally temperature dependent) parameters describing pseudo-equilibrium steps prior to and after the rate determining step. These parameters have to be obtained or estimated.

The developed methodology was applied for assessing the activation energy of ORR under HTPEM FC-relevant conditions, i.e. in concentrated H_3PO_4 environment at temperatures of 120-180 °C. The particular methodology applicable to correct calculation of the standard redox potentials $E_{ORR,T}^\circ$ and consequently $E_{ORR,T}$ depending on various changes of activities (fugacities) of reacting components and temperature was also described. It was shown that the discussion whether the product of ORR is H_2O in the gas or liquid state is irrelevant, i.e. the result is the same for both cases. Moreover, the difference between the values of ΔG^\ddagger calculated from \tilde{k}_{as}° and \tilde{k}_{dis}° is, in this particular case, insignificant. On the other hand, the ΔG^\ddagger values for both these mechanisms differ substantially from the ΔG^\ddagger value that would be (though incorrectly) obtained directly from the j_{ex} . Finally, though the above treatment was developed in context of HTPEM FC, the approach is, in principal, general and can be applied to any electrochemical reaction.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported from the grant of Specific university research – grant No. A2_FCHT_2024_016 of University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague and by Czech Science Foundation Grant No. 22-23668K and by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

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